

RECEIPT Stakeholder small-session and interview protocol

Why have an interview protocol?

With the advent of travel restrictions due to the spread of Covid-19, interviews have taken on greater importance in the RECEIPT project than originally intended. Stakeholder input is an important element in developing RECEIPT storylines for each sector. In addition to group workshops, sectoral interviews with one or two external participants are good opportunities for researchers to fill knowledge gaps and test assumptions.

This interview protocol was developed to help researchers to prepare for the interview and consider what questions will elicit relevant information. Interview protocols help ensure that key points are not forgotten during the interview. They also support the RECEIPT ethical requirements, acting as a reminder to relay important pieces of information to the interviewee, such as the purpose of the interview, what will happen to the information obtained, and any confidentiality concerns.

Number of participants:

Depending on the work package information needs, 3-5 external participants might be recruited for small online sessions and any number of additional individual interviews. Unless mutually agreed, individual interviews will be conducted privately, with no more than two interviewers involved. Ideally interviews will be recorded, or detailed notes taken, and these can be shared within the RECEIPT project. Larger workshops are more fully addressed in the stakeholder interaction protocol.

Interview risk management:

As part of ethical conduct for research engaging with people, it is prudent to assess what risks there may be to interviewers and participants. As the RECEIPT interviews will be mainly online to manage the risk of Covid-19 infection, the other risks are minimal. The interviews will generally be a maximum of 1-1.5 hours undertaken online. If in-person interviews become allowed by public health authorities, any official advice will be strictly adhered to and interviews will be conducted at a place acceptable to both interviewer and participant, such as a meeting room in a workplace, university or conference centre. Due to the professional environment and role of the participants, the interviews pose a low safety risk to the researcher. However, in all face to face interviews, a colleague will know when and where the interviews are scheduled and expect a check-in call by the end of the day.

Audio Visual permission:

All interviews will be audio recorded and visual records may be made of shared screens, notes, drawings or whiteboard collaborations. Participants will be informed in advance of the data management plans as part of the invitation process.

In advance of Interview:

Participants will be primed before the interview with information about RECEIPT and the Storyline approach which will be included in the invitation to participate and the informed consent materials. The materials will introduce the topic of remote climate risks to the EU and the method of climate

risk storylines. Before the interviews, participants will be given a short list of possible topics so they can prepare themselves and their replies.

Semi-structured Interviews or Inquiry-Based Conversations

Depending on preference, interviews can follow a semi-structured approach (Irvine, Drew, & Sainsbury, 2012) or an inquiry-based conversation approach (Castillo-Montoya, 2016). In both cases, it would be helpful if a similar initial and closing questions is asked of all participants, starting with something like this: ‘What risks are you aware of to your sector that come from weather or climate impacts?’ The interviews would all finish with a question such as: ‘Is there anything else you want to mention that might have come up while we were talking?’ While framing might be different in each sector, consistent start and finish allows for comparability across interviews.

In a **semi-structured interview**, the interviewer will cover a **series of subtopics** with all participants. The interviewer will follow an interview guide with questions and topics that need to be covered during the conversation, usually **in a particular order**. However, the interviewer is able to follow topical trajectories in the conversation that may stray from the guide when appropriate.

In the **inquiry-based conversation** approach, interview are **not scripted** and questions on any topics mentioned on the advance list might be asked. Participants might be **prompted to return to the main topic** if their responses wander to other topics where they are more eager to engage. The format follows the sequence of 1) orientation through advance materials, 2) conceptualisation at the start of the interview, 3) investigation to inform possible storylines and 4) any concluding comments.

Each work package will likely develop their own question guide. The following is a general sample.

- What risks are you aware of to your sector that come from weather or climate impacts?
- Overall, what creates vulnerabilities & risks to your sector thriving in the EU?
- Can you see similarities between pandemic and climate impact risks such as those that might affect supply and demand?
- How would you rate risks that are weather/climate sensitive on a scale of 1-5 (5 is very sensitive)?
- Where regions in other parts of the world are important for your sector thriving in the EU?
- What weather or climate impacts has your sector already experienced?
- Thinking about vulnerabilities and risks to your sector in other parts of the world, what might have the biggest impacts on Europe?
- What links the remote climate risks you mentioned to vulnerabilities in the EU?
- What information about remote climate risks is useful for long range planning in your sector?
- What regions might become more important for your sector due to climate or social change over the next 30 years?
- Is there anything else you want to mention that came up while we were talking?

Castillo-Montoya, M. (2016). Preparing for Interview Research: The Interview Protocol Refinement Framework. *The Qualitative Report*, 21(5), 81-831.

Irvine, A., Drew, P., & Sainsbury, R. (2012). ‘Am I not answering your questions properly?’ Clarification, adequacy and responsiveness in semi-structured telephone and face-to-face interviews. *Qualitative Research*, 13(1), 87-106. doi:10.1177/1468794112439086

RECEIPT Interview or workshop consent form

The RECEIPT project

RECEIPT (REmote Climate Effects and their Impact on European sustainability, Policy and Trade) is a European Horizon 2020 funded research project that was launched in September 2019. The project will map connections between potential climate risks and extremes outside of the EU and their consequences for key EU social and economic sectors and systems.

Partnerships and storylines

The RECEIPT consortium is approaching the complex nature of interconnected risks from climate change impacts by working with societal partners to develop and evaluate dedicated storylines. By combining events, stories and data in a narrative format, storylines have the potential to communicate complex issues through internally consistent chains of cause and effect, in some detail.

An important feature of this approach is the involvement of stakeholders from the start of the project, to locate sources of essential resources and identify important trade nodes as well as remote hotspots. Stakeholder expertise will help to describe hotspots considering where climate hazards have led to significant interruptions in the past or can lead to vulnerabilities in the foreseeable future.

The RECEIPT project will use the storylines to reveal the effects of climatic trends and extremes in remote areas on the European economy, give insights in how some vulnerabilities can be prevented or reduced, and potentially identify future business model opportunities.

Confidentiality of data collected during the interview or workshop

Your confidentiality is very important to us. The data collected during the interview or workshop will be kept private and access to any transcripts is restricted to the RECEIPT partner organizations. The Chatham House Rule applies during workshops (participants are free to use the information received, but neither the identity nor the affiliation of the speaker(s), nor that of any other participant, may be revealed.) Workshops will be audio recorded and photographed for research purposes only. No personally identifiable images or recordings are to be shared, including by participants, according to the Chatham House rule.

In some instances, third parties may be involved in the process of transcription and/or translation of the data collected during the interviews but no data will be retained by these parties. The data collected will be analyzed and the outputs of the study will not be attributed to you or your organization. The data collected will not be used for any purposes outside this project. In addition, you are free to withdraw from the interview or workshop at any time (up to the point at which your data is anonymized and amalgamated) by contacting the RECEIPT office (Info@receipt.eu), the interviewer or the workshop leader.

RECEIPT Interview or workshop consent form

Organization _____

Name of participant _____

Interviewer or workshop
leader _____

Workshop
Date _____

Location _____

I have read and understood the introduction page. I understand that my participation is:

1. Completely voluntary;
2. Free for withdrawal at anytime;
3. The Chatham House Rule applies during workshops (participants are free to use the information received, but neither the identity nor the affiliation of the speaker(s), nor that of any other participant, may be revealed.)
4. The answers provided may be published but my anonymity retained;
5. The data will be held securely on the RECEIPT project portal on the Zenodo repository;
6. This form and the data collected will be retained for the whole of the RECEIPT project lifetime which is expected to run until September 2023. After this time, all personal identifying information will be destroyed

I therefore consent to my participation in this study by signing below.

Signature of Participant _____

Date _____

The RECEIPT project adheres to confidentiality and data management protocols approved by the University of Leeds Research Ethics Committee (reference LTSEE-102).
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3648121